

INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA NOMA JANRI TARAQQIYOTI VA TADRIJI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Sharq va G'arb adabiyotida noma janri, ingliz adabiyotida taraqqiyoti va tadriji, shuningdek, davlat arbobi va yozuvchi Chesterfield Filip Stenxopning "O'g'ilga maktub"lari asari tahlilga tortilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: noma janri, maktublar, epistoliar janr, Chesterfield, "O'g'ilga maktub", adabiy va estetik qarashlar.

Abstract. This article analyzes the novel genre in Eastern and Western literature, its development and progress in English literature, as well as "Letters to a Son" by the statesman and writer Chesterfield Philip Stanhope.

Key words: novel genre, letters, epistolary genre, Chesterfield, "Letter to a son", literary and aesthetic views.

Malumki, noma janri Sharq va G'arb adabiyotida o'ziga xos o'rin egallagan. Jumladan, Xorazmiyning «Muhabbatnoma» Xo'jandiyning «Latofatnoma», Sayid Ahmadning «Taashshuqnoma», Yusuf Amiriynig «Dahnoma» asarlari Jomiy, Navoiy, Bobur, Furqatning o'z do'stlari va ustozlariga yozgan she'riy maktublari noma janrining eng go'zal namunalari sanaladi. Xorij, jumladan, ingliz adabiyotida ham nomalar mualliflar ijodi, ularning adabiy va estetik qarashlari haqida ma'lumot manbai sifatida ijtimoiy va ma'naviy hayotni, adabiy jarayonni aks ettirgan badiiy adabiyotning ajralmas qismidir. Inglizabon nomalar nafaqat qiziqarli voqealar, sarguzashtlar, balki san'at, tarix va siyosat haqidagi fikrlarni, yozuvchining ichki ma'naviy dunyosi tasvirini ham ifodalagan. Shuningdek, ular orqali ingliz madaniy hayotining turli qirralarini kuzatish mumkin.

XVIII asrning birinchi yarmi ingliz epistoliar adabiyotida noma janrining ajoyib namunalari jamlangan. Mashhur yozuvchi, "Gulliverning sayohatlari" asarining muallifi D.Sviftning(1667=1745) Jonson xonimga bag'ishlangan "Stella kundaligi", yozuvchi va sayohatchi Meri Uortli Montegyuning (1689-1762) Turkiyaga sayohati natijasida yozilgan, Sharq xalqlarining odob-axloqi va urf-odatlarini aks ettirgan "turkcha" maktublari, ingliz shoiri Tomas Greyning (1716-1771) do'stlariga maktublari, davlat arbobi, yozuvchi, faylasuf, tarixchi Chesterfield Filip Stenxopning(1694-1773) "O'g'ilga maktub"lari fikrimizning yorqin dalilidir.

Chesterfieldning 400 dan ortiq namunadan tashkil topgan "O'g'ilga maktub"lari uning o'g'li Stenxopga bag'ishlangan va muallif ularni o'g'li hali yoshligidayoq yozishni boshlagan. Har bir maktub "aziz o'g'lim" jumlasini bilan boshlanadi. Maktublarni o'qir ekansiz, ular uning o'g'li bilan jonli suhbat tasavvurini yaratish uchun yozilganini his qilasiz. Chesterfield bir necha yillar davomida Fransiyada yashagan. Ushbu maktublarda fransuz va ingliz madaniyatiga, tarixi, adabiyotiga xos ko'p jihatlarni uchratish mumkin. Masalan muallif 1749 yildagi maktublarida o'g'liga XVII asr fransuz shoirlari va dramaturglari asarlarini o'qishni tavsiya qiladi, uni fransuz urf-odatlarini va xulq-atvori bilan tanishtiradi, ingliz- fransuz turmush tarzini taqqoslaydi. Maktublar yevropa ma'rifatchiligining falsafiy va umumiy madaniy muammolarini chuqurroq anglashga yordam beradi.

Chesterfield asarining tili uning o'ziga xos badiiy mahoratidan, iste'dodidan darak beradi. Quyidagi parchada muallif do'st tanlash odobi, bu boradagi adashishlar, qanday jamoada bo'lish tartibi va madaniyati, muhitning inson tarbiyasiga jiddiy ta'siri borasida juda o'rinli fikrlarni keltiradi. Shuningdek, mazkur namunada barcha xalqlar uchun umumiy bo'lgan “Do'stingni kimligini ayt, men sening kimligingni aytaman” maqolining mazmun mohiyati aks etadi:

LETTER XVII LONDON, October

16, O. S. 1747

DEAR BOY: People of your age have, commonly, an unguarded frankness about them; which makes them the easy prey and bubbles of the artful and the experienced; they look upon every knave or fool, who tells them that he is their friend, to be really so; and pay that profession of simulated friendship, with an indiscreet and unbounded confidence, always to their loss, often to their ruin. Beware, therefore, now that you are coming into the world, of these preferred friendships. Receive them with great civility, but with great incredulity too; and pay them with compliments, but not with confidence. Do not let your vanity and self-love make you suppose that people become your friends at first sight, or even upon a short acquaintance. Real friendship is a slow grower and never thrives unless engrafted upon a stock of known and reciprocal merit. There is another kind of nominal friendship among young people, which is warm for the time, but by good luck, of short duration. This friendship is hastily produced, by their being accidentally thrown together, and pursuing the course of riot and debauchery. A fine friendship, truly; and well cemented by drunkenness and lewdness. It should rather be called a conspiracy against morals and good manners, and be punished as such by the civil magistrate. However, they have the impudence and folly to call this confederacy a friendship. They lend one another money, for bad purposes; they engage in quarrels, offensive and defensive for their accomplices; they tell one another all they know, and often more too, when, of a sudden, some accident disperses them, and they think no more of each other, unless it be to betray and laugh, at their imprudent confidence. Remember to make a great difference between companions and friends; for a very complaisant and agreeable companion may, and often does, prove a very improper and a very dangerous friend. People will, in a great degree, and not without reason, form their opinion of you, upon that which they have of your friends; and there is a Spanish proverb, which says very justly, TELL ME WHO YOU LIVE WITH AND I WILL TELL YOU WHO YOU ARE. One may fairly suppose, that the man who makes a knave or a fool his friend, has something very bad to do or to conceal. But, at the same time that you carefully decline the friendship of knaves and fools, if it can be called friendship, there is no occasion to make either of them your enemies, wantonly and unprovoked; for they are numerous bodies: and I, would rather choose a secure neutrality, than alliance, or war with either of them. You may be a declared enemy to their vices and follies, without being marked out by them as a personal one. Their enmity is the next dangerous thing to their friendship. Have a real reserve with almost everybody; and have a seeming reserve with almost nobody; for it is very disagreeable to seem reserved, and very dangerous not to be so. Few people find the true medium; many are ridiculously mysterious and reserved upon trifles; and many imprudently communicative of all they know.

The next thing to the choice of your friends, is the choice of your company. Endeavor, as much as you can, to keep company with people above you: there you rise, as much as you sink with

people below you; for (as I have mentioned before) you are whatever the company you keep is. Do not mistake, when I say company above you, and think that I mean with regard to, their birth: that is the least consideration; but I mean with regard to their merit, and the light in which the world considers them.

There are two sorts of good company; one, which is called the beau monde, and consists of the people who have the lead in courts, and in the gay parts of life; the other consists of those who are distinguished by some peculiar merit, or who excel in some particular and valuable art or science. For my own part, I used to think myself in company as, much above me, when I was with Mr. Addison and Mr. Pope, as if I had been with all the princes in Europe. What I mean by low company, which should by all means be avoided, is the company of those, who, absolutely insignificant and contemptible in themselves, think they are honored by being in your company; and who flatter every vice and every folly you have, in order to engage you to converse with them. The pride of being the first of the company is but too common; but it is very silly, and very prejudicial. Nothing in the world lets down a character quicker than that wrong turn.

You may possibly ask me, whether a man has it always in his power to get the best company? and how? I say, Yes, he has, by deserving it; providing he is but in circumstances which enable him to appear upon the footing of a gentleman. Merit and good-breeding will make their way everywhere. Knowledge will introduce him, and good-breeding will endear him to the best companies: for, as I have often told you, politeness and good-breeding are absolutely necessary to adorn any, or all other good qualities or talents. Without them, no knowledge, no perfection whatever, is seen in its best light. The scholar, without good-breeding, is a pedant; the philosopher, a cynic; the soldier, a brute; and every man disagreeable. [3]

Ushbu maktubning kulminatsiyasi har qanday insoniy fazilatning ibtidosi yaxshi tarbiya va xushmuomalalik, usiz mukammallikka erishib bo'lmaydi (*I have often told you, politeness and good-breeding are absolutely necessary to adorn any, or all other good qualities or talents. Without them, no knowledge, no perfection whatever, is seen in its best light. The scholar, without good-breeding, is a pedant; the philosopher, a cynic; the soldier, a brute; and every man disagreeable*) [3]

Yana bir maktubda nutq madaniyati va mahorati, nutq sanatining inson uchun ahamiyati, insonni so'zga masuliyati, nutq sofligining ko'pgina nuqsonlarni yashira olishi ko'z va quloq yurak sari eng muhim manzil ekani haqidagi didaktik fikrlarni kuzatamiz. ” *Style is the dress of thoughts; and let them be ever so just, if your style is homely, coarse, and vulgar, they will appear to as much disadvantage, and be as ill received as your person, though ever so well proportioned, would, if dressed in rags, dirt, and tatters. Constant experience has shown me, that great purity and elegance of style, with a graceful elocution, cover a multitude of faults, in either a speaker or a writer. For my own part, I confess (and I believe most people are of my mind) that if a speaker should ungracefully mutter or stammer out to me the sense of an angel, deformed by barbarism and solecisms, or larded with vulgarisms, he should never speak to me a second time, if I could help it. Gain the heart, or you gain nothing; the eyes and the ears are the only roads to the heart. Merit and knowledge will not gain hearts, though they will secure them when gained* [3]

Chesterfield Filip Stenxopning "O'g'ilga maktub"lari nafaqat o'sha davr G'arbiy Yevropa pedagogik tafakkuri tarixi uchun balki bugungi kun uchun ham katta ahamiyatga ega va

dolzarbdir. Chunki unda aynan o'g'il farzand tarbiyasiga oid muhim ahloqiy normalar, insoniy fazilatlar, haqiqiy “gentleman” bo'lib yetishishning zaruriy shartlari o'z aksini topadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati :

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